

Testing Program was also good.

ADT38 is a dwarf (80-85 cm), nonlodging, and heavy-tillering rice with a duration of 130-135 d. The grain is medium slender, fine, and white. Milling recovery is 68%, and cooking quality is good.

ADT38 was screened under artificial conditions for the important pests and diseases of the area (Table 2). It possesses resistance to blast (BI), brown spot (BS), green leafhopper (GLH), and

Table 2. Reaction of ADT38 and IR20 to insect pests and diseases under controlled screening.

Variety	Score ^a								
	BI	BB	RTV	BS	BPH	WBPH	GLH	LF	GM
ADT38	0	7	5	2	5	1	3	5	5
IR20	3	5	9	2	7	9	9	9	9

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice.

whitebacked planthopper (WBPH). It is also moderately resistant to tungro (RTV), brown planthopper (BPH), leaffolder (LF), and gall midge (GM). □

Comparison of IR36 and Local varieties of rice in farmers' fields in Bhutan

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In the Wangdiphodrang-Punakha valley, interest in modern fertilizer-responsive, high-yielding rice varieties is growing. Production of acceptable amounts of straw for animal fodder in winter is also important. We studied the performance of IR36 at 13 sites in the valley at altitudes between 1,200 and 1,450 m. Data were analyzed as a randomized complete block design, with sites as blocks and variety-management combinations as treatments.

Soils were sandy to clay loam, pH 4.5-6.2, with 1% organic C or less, and low (<10 ppm) to moderate (15-20 ppm) Olsen available P. Soil fertility is maintained by annual additions of an average 7 t farmyard manure (FYM)/ ha. At most study sites, farmers applied an estimated 9-14 t FYM/ha, but some sites received none.

In late May and in June, farmers transplanted 37- to 60-d-old IR36 seedlings adjacent to the local variety in terraced fields so that, at each site, about one-half to two-thirds of a typical field was planted to IR36 and the rest to the local variety. The crops were managed following local practices. A portion of the IR36 plot (separated from the rest of the IR36 by a bund) had improved

Mean yields of IR36 and local rice varieties in 13 farmers' fields.^a Wangdiphodrang-Punakha valley, Bhutan, 1986.

Site	Local management				Improved management ^b	
	Local variety		IR36		IR36	
	Grain ^c (t/ha)	Straw ^d (t/ha)	Grain ^c (t/ha)	Straw ^d (t/ha)	Grain ^c (t/ha)	Straw ^d (t/ha)
1 ^e	5.16	17.13	4.46	na	4.14	na
2	4.52	15.60	4.99	5.27	5.48	5.80
3 ^f	3.11	na	3.36	na	4.72	na
4	4.29	12.90	4.43	na	5.76	na
5	4.88	15.40	6.66	11.06	7.86	10.00
6 ^{eg}	3.79	11.80	3.62	na	4.43	na
7	4.28	na	5.87	na	5.92	na
8	2.93	na	4.59	6.93	5.30	9.80
9	4.21	14.20	5.39	na	7.05	na
10 ^f	3.92	10.80	4.22	5.80	4.16	6.40
11 ^f	3.77	12.20	4.72	na	3.91	na
12	4.18	12.14	4.91	6.66	6.63	9.46
13	5.69	25.40	7.69	17.07	8.70	19.40
Mean	4.21	14.76	4.96	8.79	5.69	10.14
Grain increase (%) over local	0	-	17.7	-	34.7	-
MBCR ^h	0	-	5.3	-	6.8	-
LSD (0.05) grain over all sites				0.56		
CV (%) grain over all sites				14		

^a na = not available. ^b 35 kg N/ha plus weeding at 30-40 DT. ^c At 14% moisture content. ^d Fresh weight at harvest. ^e IR36 affected by severe weed competition. ^f IR36 adversely affected by water stress at tillering or flowering. ^g Low soil fertility. ^h Based on rice seed cost of \$30/ha, urea plus application cost of \$46/ha, rough rice price of \$0.21/kg.

management: urea topdressing and weeding at panicle initiation (30-40 d after transplanting [DT]). Grain yields were estimated from replicated 5-m² crop cuts from the local variety and IR36 under local and improved management at each site. Where possible, straw yield at harvest was also obtained.

IR36 was susceptible to drought at the nursery stage, and at two sites where water shortage was prolonged, farmers' IR36 seedlings had to be replaced with

seedlings from CARD. Pests and diseases were insignificant during the study. IR36 crop duration (161-177 d, mean 170) allowed harvest 4 to 30 d (mean 9 d) earlier than most of the local varieties.

IR36 grain yield was 18% higher (P=0.05) than that of the local varieties averaged over sites (see table). With improved management, IR36 yielded 35% more grain (P=0.05) than local varieties. At individual sites, IR36 grain yield was 3.6-7.7 t/ha for farmers'

practice, and 3.9-8.7 t/ha for improved practice, largely reflecting site fertility (see table). The low IR36 yields at some sites was attributed to severe weed pressure, low soil fertility where farmers applied no FYM, and prolonged water stress at tillering and flowering.

The grain yield increase obtained with IR36 was economically attractive. The

marginal benefit-cost ratio (MBCR) was estimated at 5.3 with local practice and 6.8 with improved practice (see table).

The data indicate that, with better management and on more fertile sites, short-statured IR36 could produce as much straw as the local varieties (11-19 t/ha), but that under average conditions straw productivity may be

inferior.

IR36 has the potential for high yield in the valley; however, its susceptibility to drought, lack of cold tolerance at the reproductive phase (important where rather late planting is common), and seemingly inadequate straw production preclude its wide promotion. □

DAK83 – a promising new aromatic selection for small holders in Tanzania

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Rice in Tanzania is grown predominantly by subsistence farmers. Their acceptance of a variety is determined mainly by its cooking and eating qualities. Supa India, with excellent grain quality, is widely grown, although it has several agronomic deficiencies.

A breeding program to develop an improved variety with high yield potential and acceptable grain quality was initiated at DARC in 1982. Crosses were made between Supa and elite pedigree lines that were derivatives of Supa crosses made in Zanzibar. Several selections possessing intermediate plant type, earliness, and aromatic, long to medium-slender grains were isolated.

DAK83-99-27-3 (DAK83) is a pregony selection from Supa India/ Line 302D (selected pedigree line from BKN6820/Supa India). It has intermediate aroma, high yield potential, and short growth duration. It was further tested in yield trials at four sites during 1985 and 1986 wet and dry seasons (see table). It yielded 3.6-7.5 t/ha, with an average of 5.2 t/ha – higher by 1.7 t/ha than the average yield of Supa.

DAK83 has average plant height of 106 cm with no tendency to lodge even at 120 kg N/ha. It matures almost a month earlier (110 d) than Supa (135+ d), and more uniformly. Its

Grain yield of DAK83 in different trials at 4 sites in Tanzania, 1985-86.

Location	Entries tested (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)				Rank of DAK83
		Highest	DAK83	Lowest	Check ^a	
<i>1985 wet season</i>						
Dakawa	6	7.7	5.6	4.2	4.2 (IR579)	2
Dakawa	15	9.4	7.5	3.1	6.1 (Katrin)	3
Dakawa	5	4.7	3.6	2.5	2.5 (Katrin)	3
<i>1985 dry season</i>						
Dakawa ^{b9}	5.6	1.8 ^c		1.4	3.3 (Katrin)	7
<i>1986 wet season</i>						
Dakawa	5	6.2	5.3	5.0	5.1 (IR579)	2
Dakawa	15	7.1	5.0	4.5	3.5 (Supa)	5
Dakawa	30	5.8	4.7	2.8	3.9 (IR60)	6
Mbeya-Igurusi	9	7.9	4.8	3.0	3.8 (Kahogo)	6
Tabora-Mwamapuli	6	4.4	4.1	1.5	1.5 (Supa)	2
DRF-Farms	6	5.5	4.2	3.3	3.9 (IRE)	2

^aCheck variety names in parentheses. ^bIrrigated. ^c60% bird damage.

cooking and eating qualities are not significantly different from those of Supa. Farmers' acceptance of DAK83 is

higher than that for newly released nonaromatic cultivars. □

CR314-5-10: a promising culture for shallow rainfed lands of the Chhotanagpur plateau region of Bihar

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Chhotanagpur has 1.23 million ha under rice cultivation in wet season; of this, 4% is irrigated and the remaining rainfed. The rainfed area is further classified into dryland (11%), shallow rainfed bunded upland with 0-30 cm water depth (55%), intermediate rainfed with 30-100 cm water depth (27%) and deepwater with

Table 1. Performance of CR314-5-10 and check variety Ratna under direct seeded conditions at Hazaribag and Kanke, Bihar, India, 1984-85.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering		Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Hazaribag	Kanke	Hazaribag		Kanke 1984
			1984	1985	
CR314-5-10	89	93	3.8	2.7	4.2
Ratna	91	94	2.7	2.0	2.6
LSD (P = 0.05)			0.6	0.3	0.8
Increase (%) over Ratna			40		60